

3-D modeling of the influence of irradiation on the electrical power of a single-sided polycrystalline silicon photocell subjected to multi-spectral illumination

Mayoro Dieye^{*1,2}, Nacire Mbengue² and Awa Dieye^{1,2}

¹*Research Doctor, Department of Physics, Science Faculty of Dakar, University Cheikh Anta Diop of Dakar (UCAD), Dakar-Senegal.

²Associate Professor - Research Professor, Semiconductor optoelectronics group, Science Faculty of Dakar (UCAD), Dakar-Senegal

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present a 3-dimensional modeling of the influence of irradiation on the electrical power of a single-sided polycrystalline silicon photocell subjected to multi-spectral illumination. Indeed, solving the continuity equation in a 3-D study model allowed us to establish the current density, photovoltage and diode current density. From these, the expression of the electrical power of the photopile is deduced and then studied as a function of the recombination rate at the junction and the irradiation.

Key words: Monofacial photocell, Recombination rate at the junction, Irradiation, Electrical power, Polycrystalline

1. INTRODUCTION

The quality of a solar cell is closely related to its electrical and electronic properties, characterized by recombination rates, grain boundaries, grain size, and electrical power, among others. Also, some external factors such as irradiation can influence the quality of the solar cell [1], [4]. These factors are the recombination's of photo generated minority carriers in volume (Shockley-Read-Hall, Auger and radiative) [5], and in surface, photo current and photo voltage losses, shading effects, resistive losses, ... In this paper, we present a three-dimensional (3D) study of the influence of irradiation on the electrical power of a polycrystalline silicon single-facet solar cell under intense multi-spectral illumination [6].

2. MODELING AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

A bifacial solar cell is a device which generates electricity directly from visible light. When light quanta are absorbed, electron hole pairs are generated as it can be seen in **Fig. 1(a)**. An n^+ - p - p^+ poly crystalline solar cell, made of many small individual grains, is considered. Taking into account of the physical process simulation, the 2D representation of the solar cell is illustrated in Fig. 1(a) and in Fig. 1(b), the fibrously oriented columnar grain is considered. At the junction, n^+ - p interface ($z=0$), S_{fu} quantifies how the excess carriers flow through the junction in actual operating conditions and then S_{fu} characterizes how electrons cross to the junction [7], [9] and [11]. At the back side of the solar cell, (S_{bu}) is used to translate the losses in this zone. It quantifies hence, the rate at which excess minority carriers are lost at the back side of the cell [5], [7] and [12].

2.1. Excess Minority Carriers Density

The solar cell's emitter is considered as a dead zone. So, the excess minority carriers density is determined taking account into only the contribution of the solar cell's base.

Fig. 1: (a-left) 2D representation of the monofacial solar cell [13]; **(b-right)** 3D representation of the solar cell
 $H = 130 \mu\text{m}$, $D = 26 \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

Considering the emitter as a dead area, the excess minority carrier distribution in the base, seen as a greater contribution to the photo-conversion, is derived from the continuity equation [12], [14]:

$$D(Kl, \phi) \times \left[\frac{\partial^2 \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial z^2} \right] - \frac{\delta(x, y, z)}{\tau} + G(z) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$D(Kl, \phi)$ is the diffusion coefficient in the presence of irradiation. It is expressed as follows:

$$D(Kl, \phi) = \frac{L(Kl, \phi)^2}{\tau} \quad (2)$$

In this expression, $G(z)$ represents the generation rate of minority charge carriers in the base [13] whose expression is given by the following equation:

$$G(z) = \sum_{i=1}^3 a_i \times \exp(-b_i \times z) \quad (3)$$

The values a_i and b_i are the values tabulated from the modeling of the absorption spectrum of the photocell for AM 1.5 [8], [20], [21].

L depend on the irradiation energy Φ and the damage coefficient Kl through the following expression [29]-[31]:

$$L(Kl, \phi) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\frac{1}{L_0^2} + Kl \times \phi}} \quad (4)$$

L_0 is the diffusion length without irradiation.

The solution of the equation can be written as follows [8], [14], [15]:

$$\delta(x, y, z) = \sum_k \sum_j Z_{k,j}(z) \times \cos(C_k \times x) \cdot \cos(C_j \times y) \quad (5)$$

k, j : are the indices for the x and y directions respectively.

C_k and C_j are obtained from the conditions at the grain boundaries $\pm \frac{g_x}{2}$ et $\pm \frac{g_y}{2}$ [8] [14] [21] [22]:

$$\left[\frac{\partial \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial x} \right]_{x=\pm \frac{g_x}{2}} = \mp \frac{Sgb}{D(Kl, \phi)} \delta\left(\pm \frac{g_x}{2}, y, z\right) \quad (6)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial y} \right]_{y=\pm \frac{g_y}{2}} = \mp \frac{Sgb}{D(Kl, \phi)} \delta\left(x \pm \frac{g_y}{2}, z\right) \quad (7)$$

g_x is the grain width, g_y the grain length Sgb the recombination velocity at the grain boundaries.

From equations (6) and (7) we obtain two transcendental equations [32] which are:

$$\tan\left(C_k \times \frac{g_x}{2}\right) = \frac{Sgb}{2.C_k \times D(Kl, \phi)} \quad (8)$$

$$\tan\left(C_j \times \frac{g_y}{2}\right) = \frac{Sgb}{2.C_j \times D(Kl, \phi)} \quad (9)$$

By replacing $\delta(x, y, z)$ in the continuity equation and the fact that the cosine function is orthogonal, we obtain the following differential equation:

$$Z_{k,j} = A_{k,j} \times \cosh\left(\frac{z}{L_{k,j}}\right) + B_{k,j} \times \sinh\left(\frac{z}{L_{k,j}}\right) - \sum_{i=1}^3 K_{i,j,k} \times \exp(-b_i \times z) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Or } K_{i,j,k} = \frac{L_{k,j}^2}{D_{k,j} \times [b_i^2 \times L_{k,j}^2 - 1]} \times a_i \quad (11)$$

$$\text{With : } L_{k,j} = \left[C_k^2 + C_j^2 + \frac{1}{L(Kl, \phi)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{And } D_{k,j} = D(Kl, \phi) \times \frac{[C_k \times g_x + \sin(C_k \times g_x)][C_j \times g_y + \sin(C_j \times g_y)]}{16 \cdot \sin\left(C_k \times \frac{g_x}{2}\right) \cdot \sin\left(C_j \times \frac{g_y}{2}\right)} \quad (13)$$

The coefficients $A_{k,j}$ and $B_{k,j}$ are calculated from the following boundary conditions [7], [14], [23], [27]:

At the junction ($z = 0$):

$$\left[\frac{\partial \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial z} \right]_{z=0} = \frac{Sf}{D(Kl, \phi)} \delta(x, y, 0) \quad (14)$$

Sf is the junction recombination velocity, written as [7], [14], [25], [27] $Sf = Sf_0 + Sf_j$ with Sf_0 being the intrinsic junction recombination velocity related to the shunt resistance due to losses occurring across the junction and Sf_j is the imposed junction recombination velocity due external load. It defines the current flow that is the operating point of the cell. For each illumination mode, the intrinsic junction recombination velocity was calculated using the method described in [7], [14], [25], [27].

At the back side ($z = \omega b$):

$$\left[\frac{\partial \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial z} \right]_{z=\omega b} = -\frac{Sb}{D(Kl, \phi)} \delta(x, y, \omega b) \quad (15)$$

Sb is the back surface recombination velocity. It quantifies the rate at which excess minority carriers are lost at the back surface of the cell [7], [14], [25], [27]. The derivation of the photocurrent with respect to Sf , provides for each illumination mode the expression of Sb , as in [7], [14], [25], [27].

$$A_{k,j} = \sum_{i=1}^3 K_{i,k,j} \times \frac{\frac{1}{L_{k,j}} \left(\frac{Sf}{D(Kl, \phi)} - b_i \right) \times \exp(-b_i \times \omega b) + Y_{k,j} \left(\frac{Sf}{D(Kl, \phi)} + b_i \right)}{\frac{Sf \times Y_{k,j} + X_{k,j}}{D(Kl, \phi)} + \frac{X_{k,j}}{L_{k,j}}} \quad (16)$$

$$B_{k,j} = \sum_{i=1}^3 K_{i,k,j} \times \frac{\frac{Sf}{D(Kl, \phi)} \left(\frac{Sb}{D(Kl, \phi)} - b_i \right) \times \exp(-b_i \times \omega b) + X_{k,j} \left(\frac{Sf}{D(Kl, \phi)} + b_i \right)}{\frac{Sf \times Y_{k,j} + X_{k,j}}{D(Kl, \phi)} + \frac{X_{k,j}}{L_{k,j}}} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Avec: } X_{k,j} = \frac{1}{L_{k,j}} \times \sinh\left(\frac{\omega b}{L_{k,j}}\right) + \frac{Sb}{D(Kl, \phi)} \times \cosh\left(\frac{\omega b}{L_{k,j}}\right) \quad (18)$$

$$Y_{k,j} = \frac{1}{L_{k,j}} \times \cosh\left(\frac{\omega b}{L_{k,j}}\right) + \frac{Sb}{D(Kl, \phi)} \times \sinh\left(\frac{\omega b}{L_{k,j}}\right) \quad (19)$$

2.2. Photocurrent density

The photocurrent density can be calculated by the following equation [8] [14] [16] [17] [24]:

$$J_{ph} = \frac{q \times D(Kl, \phi)}{g_x \times g_y} \cdot \int_{-\frac{g_x}{2}}^{+\frac{g_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{g_y}{2}}^{+\frac{g_y}{2}} \left[\frac{\partial \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial z} \right]_{z=0} dx \cdot dy \quad (20)$$

After calculation we get:

$$J_{ph}(Sf, Kl, \phi) = q \times \sum_{k=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 R_{k,j} \times Sf \cdot \sum_{i=1}^3 K_{i,k,j} \cdot \frac{\frac{Sb - D(Kl, \phi) \times b_i}{D(Kl, \phi)} \times \frac{X_{k,j}}{Y_{k,j}} + b_i \times L_{k,j}}{\frac{X_{k,j} + Sf \times L_{k,j}}{Y_{k,j}} + D(Kl, \phi)} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{With: } R_{k,j} = \frac{4 \cdot \sin\left(C_k \times \frac{g_x}{2}\right) \times \sin\left(C_k \times \frac{g_y}{2}\right)}{g_x \times g_y \times C_k \times C_j} \quad (22)$$

q is the charge of the electron.

2.3. Photovoltage

Using the Boltzmann's relation, the photo voltage V_{ph} can be expressed as [8], [14], [16]:

$$V_{ph} = V_T \cdot \ln \left\{ 1 + \frac{N_b}{n_i} \cdot \int_{-\frac{g_x}{2}}^{+\frac{g_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{g_y}{2}}^{+\frac{g_y}{2}} \delta(x, y, z) dx \cdot dy \right\} \quad (23)$$

When the photocell is illuminated simultaneously by the front and rear sides, the photovoltage is given by the following expression:

$$V_{ph} = V_T \cdot \ln \left\{ 1 + \frac{N_b}{n_i^2} \cdot \sum_{k=0}^4 \sum_{j=0}^4 R_{k,j} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^3 K_{i,k,j} \cdot \frac{Sb - D(Kl, \phi) b_i \cdot \exp(-b_i \times H) - \frac{X_{k,j}}{Y_{k,j}} + b_i \times L_{k,j}}{D(Kl, \phi) Y_{k,j} + \frac{X_{k,j}}{Y_{k,j}} + \frac{Sf \times L_{k,j}}{D(Kl, \phi)}} \right\} \quad (24)$$

Où $V_T = \frac{k \times T}{q}$ is the thermal voltage, k the Boltzmann constant, N_b the base doping rate and n_i the intrinsic carrier concentration.

2.4. Diode current

Its expression is given by the relation [18]:

$$J_d = q \times Sf \cdot \left[1 + \frac{N_b}{n_i^2} \cdot \int_{-\frac{g_x}{2}}^{+\frac{g_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{g_y}{2}}^{+\frac{g_y}{2}} \left[\frac{\partial \delta(x, y, z)}{\partial z} \right]_{z=0} dx \cdot dy \right] \quad (25)$$

2.5. Solar Cell's Electric Power

The power generated by the cell is given by [19]:

$$P(Sf, Sb, g, Sgb, Kl, \phi) = V_{ph}(Sf, Sb, g, Sgb, Kl, \phi) \times J(Sf, Sb, g, Sgb, Kl, \phi) \quad (26)$$

$$\text{With : } J(Sf, Sb, g, Sgb, Kl, \phi) = J_{ph}(Sf, Sb, g, Sgb, Kl, \phi) - J_d(Sf, Sb, g, Sgb, Kl, \phi) \quad (27)$$

The solar cell's generated power depends on Sf and then is function of the solar cell's real operating point varying from the short-circuit operating point to the open one

3. RESULTS

In **Fig. 2** and **3** we present the profiles, in three dimensions, of the electrical power of the photocell as a function of the recombination rate at the junction, the irradiation energy Φ and the damage coefficient Kl .

Fig. 2: Electrical power as a function of recombination rate at the Sf_j junction and irradiation energy for grain size $g=0.095$ cm.

($H=0,03$ cm; $Sgb=4,5 \cdot 10^4$ cm/s; $Kl=10,5$ cm²/MeV).

Fig. 3: Electrical power as a function of the recombination rate at the junction Sf_j and the damage coefficient Kl for a grain size $g=0,11$ cm.

($H=0,03$ cm; $Sgb=5 \cdot 10^4$ cm/s; $\Phi=100$ MeV)

We can see in figure 2 that the electrical power of the silicon solar cell decreases with the increase of the irradiation energy; indeed, if the irradiation energy increases, the degradations will increase to some extent leading to a decrease (small here) of the available power.

For figure 3, the increase of the damage coefficient accentuates the decrease of the electrical power of the silicon solar cell. This can be explained by the fact that the increase of the damage coefficient translates into an increase of the probability of creation of defects by irradiation, thus more important degradation of the solar cell, i.e. more important leakages. Thus, the material becomes more sensitive to the degradation caused by possible particles and thus the photovoltage will be all the more degraded as the damage coefficient will increase.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have shown that the electrical power of the solar cell decreases with the irradiation. It was shown that the increase of the irradiation energy and of the damage coefficient degrades more or less the parameters of the photocell. For the effect of the damage coefficient, it was shown that this was noticeable especially from a certain irradiation energy.

REFERENCES

- [1]. H. W. Kraner. (1983), Radiation damage in silicon detectors. 2nd Pisa Meeting on advanced detector, Grosseto, Italy, June 3-7.
- [2]. G-H. Shin, K-S Ryu, H-M Kim, K-W Min. (march 2008), Radiation effect test for single-crystalline and polycrystalline silicon solar cells. *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, Vol. 52, No. 3, pp. 843-847
- [3]. R. J. Walters, S.R. Messenger, G.P. Summers, A.W. Bett, F. Dimroth, C. Baur, M. Meusel, T. Takamoto, T. Agui, M. Imaizumi, S. Matsuda. (2001), Radiation response analysis of triple junction InGaP/InGaAs/Ge solar cells. 17th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference, pp. 2251-2254.
- [4]. K. Iniewski. Radiation effects in semiconductors, CRC Press, Vol.7928, 2011, ISBN 978-1-4419-6017-7.
- [5]. Saïdou Madougou, Mohamadou Kaka and Gregoire Sissoko, (2010) Silicon solar cells: recombination and electrical parameters. *Solar Energy*, Book edited by: Radu D. Rugesco, ISBN 978-953-307-052-0, pp. 432, February
- [6]. F. Pelanchon, C. Sudre and Y. Moreau, (12-16 October, 1992), Solar Cells under Intense Light Concentration: Numerical and Analytical Approaches, 11th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference, Montreux, Suisse.
- [7]. Sissoko, G., Museruka, C., Correa, A., Gaye, I. and Ndiaye, A.L. (1996) Light Spectral Effect on Recombination Parameters of Silicon Solar Cell. *Proceedings of World Renewable Energy Congress*, Denver, USA, pp.1487-1490.
- [8]. Dugas, J. (1994) 3D Modelling of a Reverse Cell Made with Improved Multicrystalline Silicon Waf Solar Energy Materials & Solar Cells, 32, 71-88. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0927-0248\(94\)90257-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0927-0248(94)90257-7)
- [9]. Barro, F.I., Mbodji, S., Ndiaye, M., Maiga, A.S. and Sissoko, G. (2008) Bulk and Surface Recombination Parameters Measurement of Silicon Solar Cell under Constant White Bias Light. *Journal des Sciences*, 8, 37-41.
- [10]. Nzonzolo, Lilonga-Boyenga, D. and Sissoko, G. (2014) Illumination Level Effects on Macroscopic Parameters of a Bifacial Solar Cell. *Energy and Power Engineering*, 6, pp. 25-36. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/epe.2014.63004>
- [11]. Zerbo, I., Zougrana, M., Ouedraogo, A., Korgo, B., Zouma, B. and Bathiebo, D.J. (2014) Influence of Electromagnetic Waves Produced by an Amplitude Modulation Radio Antenna on the Electric Power Delivered by a Silicon Solar Cell. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 20, 139-148. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/gjpas.v20i2.9>
- [12]. Mbodji, S., Mbow, B., Barro, F.I. and Sissoko, G. (2011) A 3D Model for Thickness and Diffusion Capacitance of Emitter-Base Junction Determination in a Bifacial Polycrystalline Solar Cell under Real Operating Condition. *Turkish Journal of Physics*, 15, 281-291.
- [13]. Ndoye, S., Ndiaye, M., Diao, A., Dione, M.M., Diarisso, D., Bama, A.O.N., Ly, I., Sow, G., Maiga, A.S., Foulani, A., Barro, F.I. and Sissoko, G. (2010) Modeling and Simulating the Powering System of a Base Transmitter Station with a Standalone Photovoltaic Generator. *Proceedings of 25th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition*, pp. 5208-5211.
- [14]. H. L. Diallo, A. Wereme, A. S. Maïga and G. Sissoko (2008) New approach of both Junction and back surface recombination velocities in a 3D modeling study of a Polycrystalline silicon solar cell. *Eur. Phys. J. Appl. Phys.*, 42, pp.203–211.
- [15]. M.C Halder and T.R. Williams (1983) Grain boundary effects in polycrystalline Silicon Solar Cells I. Solution of the three- Dimensional diffusion equation by the Green's function method, *Solar Cells*, Vol. 8, N° 3, pp. 201-223.
- [16]. M. M. Dione, I. Ly, A. Diao, S. Gueye, A. Gueye, M. Thiame, G. Sissoko, (2013) Determination of the impact of the grain size and the recombination velocity at grain boundary on the values of the electrical parameters of a bifacial polycrystalline silicon solar cell, *IRACST – Engineering Science and Technology: International Journal*,

- Vol. 3 N^o. 1, pp. 66-73
- [17]. Adel Ben Arab, (1995) Photovoltaic properties and high efficiency of preferentially doped polysilicon solar cells *Solid-State Electronics*, Vol. 38, N^o 8, pp 1441-1447.
- [18]. Alfred Dieng, Ndeye Thiam, Mamadou Lamine Samb, Amadou Seïdou Maïga, Fabé Idrissa Barro, Grégoire Sissoko, (2009), Etude a 3d d'une photopile polycrystalline au silicium: influence de la taille de grain et de la vitesse de recombinaison aux joints de grain sur les paramètres électriques, *Journal des sciences*, Vol. 9, N^o 1, pp. 51-63. <http://www.ucadjds.org>.
- [19]. H. Shimizu, K. Kinamery, N. Honma and Chusuke Munakata Japanese, (1987) Determination of Surface Charge and Interface Trap Densities in Naturally Oxidize n-type Si Wafers Using Surface Photovoltages, *journal of applied physics*, Vol.26, N^o .12, pp. 2033-2036.
- [20]. J. Oualid and C. M. Singal, (1984), Influence of illumination on the grain boundaries recombination velocity in silicon, *J. Appl. Phys.* 55(4), 15 feb., pp 1195-1205.
- [21]. S. R. Dhariwal, (1988), Photocurrent and photovoltage from polycrystalline p-n junction Solar Cells, Vol. 25, pp 223-233.
- [22]. Nzonzolo, Lilonga-Boyenga, D., Mabika, C.N. and Sissoko, G. (2016), Two-Dimensional Finite Element Method Analysis Effect of the Recombination Velocity at the Grain Boundaries on the Characteristics of a Polycrystalline Silicon Solar Cell. *Circuits and Systems*, 7, 4186-4200. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/cs.2016.713344>,
- [23]. Y. L. B. Bocande, A. Correa, I. Gaye, M. L. Sow and G. Sissoko; (1994), Bulk and surfaces parameters determination in high efficiency Si solar cells. *Renewable Energy*, Vol 5, part III, pp. 1698-1700, Pergamon, pp. 0960-1481.
- [24]. H. El Ghitani and S. Martinuzzi, (1989), Influence of dislocations on electrical properties of large grained polycrystalline silicon cells. I. *Model. J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 66, N^o4. Pp. 1717-1722.
- [25]. S. Mbodji, M. Dieng, B. Mbow, F.I. Barro and G. Sissoko, (2010), Three dimensional simulated modelling of diffusion capacitance of polycrystalline bifacial silicon solar cell. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Technology (JAST)* Vol. 15, Nos. 1 & 2, pp. 109 - 114; <http://www.inasp.info/ajol>
- [26]. M. Ndiaye, A. Diao, M. Thiame, M. M. Dione, H. LY. Diallo, M. L. Samb, I. Ly, C. Gassama, S. mbodji, F. I. Barro and G. Sissoko, (2010), D Approach for a Modelling Study of the Diffusion Capacitance's Efficiency of the Solar Cell; *Proceedings of 25 th European Photovoltaic Solar Energy Conference and Exhibition, Valencia, Spain*, pp. 484-487.
- [27]. G. Sissoko, E. Nanéma, A. Corrêa, P. M. Biteye, M. Adj, A. L. Ndiaye, (1998) Silicon Solar cell recombination parameters determination using the characteristic. *Renewable Energy*, Vol-3, pp.1848-1851 Elsevier Science Ltd, 0960-1481/98/#.
- [28]. Jose Furlan and Slavko Amon, (1985), Approximation of the carrier generation rate in illuminated silicon, *Solid State Electr*, Vol.28, No.12, p.1241-1243.
- [29]. R. J. Walters and G. P. Summers, (2002), Space Radiation Effects in Advanced Solar Cell Materials and Devices *Mat. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.* Vol. 692, pp. 569-580.
- [30]. M.A. Ould El Moujtaba, M. Ndiaye, A. Diao, M. Thiame, I.F. Barro and G. Sissoko., (2012), Theoretical Study of the Influence of Irradiation on a Silicon Solar Cell under Multispectral Illumination. *Research Journal of Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology*, 4(23): pp. 5068-5073.
- [31]. R. K. Ahrenkiel, D. J. Dunlavy, H. C. Hamaker, R. T. Green, C. R. Lewis, R. E. Hayes, H. Fardi, (1986), Time-of-flight studies of minority-carrier diffusion in AlxGa1-xAs homojunctions *J. Appl. Phys.* 49(12).
- [32]. M. M. Deme, S. Mbodji, S. Ndoeye, A. Thiam, A. Dieng and G. Sissoko, (2010) Influence of illumination incidence angle, grain size and grain boundary recombination Velocity on the facial solar cell diffusion capacitance; *Revue des Energies Renouvelable* Vol. 13 N^o. 1, pp. 109-121.